

**A new name for plants previously called *Parablechnum christii* (Blechnaceae) in
Costa Rica and Panama**

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ABSTRACT

The name *Parablechnum christii* (C. Chr.) Gasper & Salino has been applied to a small species with few pairs of short pinnae that is endemic to Costa Rica and Panama. After reviewing type material of this name, we conclude that it has been misapplied and is, in fact, a synonym of *P. falciforme* (Liebm.) Gasper & Salino, an older name. Because the specimens previously identified as *P. christii* lack a name, we propose *P. talamancanum* S. Molino & R.C. Moran for these plants. The species is endemic to the mountains of Costa Rica and Panama, from 1200–3350 m.

Keywords: *Blechnum*, ferns, *Lomaria spissa*, *Parablechnum falciforme*, pteridophyte, taxonomy.

RESUMEN

Parablechnum christii (C. Chr.) Gasper & Salino es un nombre que se ha aplicado a una especie de pequeño tamaño, con pocos pares de pinnas cortas, endémica de Costa Rica y Panamá. Después de revisar el material tipo de este nombre, llegamos a la conclusión de que se ha aplicado erróneamente y es, de hecho, un sinónimo de *P. falciforme* (Liebm.) Gasper & Salino, un nombre más antiguo. Dado que los especímenes previamente identificados como *P. christii* carecen de nombre, proponemos *Parablechnum talamancanum* S. Molino & R.C. Moran para estas plantas. La especie es endémica de las montañas de Costa Rica y Panamá, entre 1200–3350 m.

Palabras clave: *Blechnum*, helechos, *Lomaria spissa*, *Parablechnum falciforme*, taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION

Parablechnum C. Presl. (Blechnaceae) is characterized by terrestrial habit, 1-pinnate leaves, sessile or short-stalked pinnae, presence of hydathodes, and (almost always) strong sterile-fertile leaf dimorphy. It is the largest genus of Blechnaceae, comprising about 68 species, most of which occur in the American tropics and the southern Pacific. The genus also occurs, but is less diverse, in southern Africa, Madagascar, and the Mascarenes (Gasper et al., 2016; Molino, 2022). Central America harbors about 10 species of *Parablechnum*, one of which has been called *P. christii* (C. Chr.) Gasper & Salino (e.g., by Moran, 1995, as “*Blechnum christii* C. Chr.”; Gasper et al., 2016). This species, which is endemic to Costa Rica and Panama (Moran, 1995), is the subject of the present paper.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We examined herbarium material previously identified as *Parablechnum christii* and the morphologically similar *P. falciforme*. We also examined the type specimens of *Blechnum christii* C. Chr. (nom. nov. for *Lomaria spissa* Christ, nom. illeg., non Fée 1852), and *L. falciformis* Liebm., to assess their conspecificity based on morphological characters. The specimens were from the following institutions: B, F, MACB, MO, P, NY, US and VT (Thiers, 2023, continuously updated). In addition, we studied high-

resolution digital images of specimens from C, CR, GOET, L and UC. Images from the latter herbaria have been consulted in the official web pages of the herbaria, in GBIF (2023a), JSTOR Global Plants platform (Ryan, 2018), and in PteridoPortal (2022). Specimens examined in situ are indicated by “!” and those viewed digitally by “! image.”

We also observed sporangia and spores from some of the specimens. Observation of sporangia was carried out by scraping the sori from previously softened and rinsed pinnae. Spores were mounted in tap water and measured with a high-powered light microscope ($\times 1,200$). At least 30 spores per specimen were measured for polar and equatorial diameters of the exine (a.k.a., “exospore”), excluding the perine (a.k.a., “perispore”). The measurements were made using the software Piximètre (Henriot & Cheype, 2022). To observe the perines and exines in detail, we used a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The samples were mounted on metal stubs with carbon adhesive, coated with a gold, and then observed under a JSM 6400 JEOL SEM operating at 20 kv. The observations were carried out at the Centro Nacional de Microscopía Electrónica (CNME) of the Universidad Complutense de Madrid.

The distribution map of the new species was generated using QGIS 3.16.8. The data were downloaded from GBIF (2013b).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The name *Blechnum christii* (here recognized as *Parablechnum christii*) was misapplied by Moran (1995). Its type (Fig. 1), not seen by Moran (1995), will key to *B. falciforme* (Liebm.) C.Chr. (= *P. falciforme* (Liebm.) Gasper & Salino) in both Moran (1995) and Mickel & Smith (2004). *Parablechnum falciforme* is characterized by leaves 41–127 cm long, chartaceous laminae, 12–35 pairs of pinnae, and pinnae 10–22 cm long (Molino, 2022). In contrast, *B. christii* sensu Moran (1995) has leaves 23–68 cm long, coriaceous laminae, fewer than 11 pairs of pinnae, and pinnae 2.5–12.3 cm long. Because both species have pinnae 1–3 cm wide (Moran, 1995; Molino, 2022), the longer pinnae of *B. falciforme* appear narrower compared to those of the *P. christii*, which has shorter pinnae that appear relatively wider. The length/width ratios of the pinnae of the two species are, respectively, 4.6–10.6 vs. 2.8–7.6.

Besides macromorphological differences, *Parablechnum falciforme* and *P. christii* sensu Moran (1995) differ in micromorphological characters. The plants previously identified as *P. christii* have 28–30 annulus cells, whereas *P. falciforme* has 19–29. Also, the perines of both species differ markedly, with the plants previously called *P. christii* having cristate-reticulate perines with the broad folds or ridges forming large areolae and surfaces with few or no filaments (Fig. 2A, B), whereas those of *P. falciforme* have cristate-reticulate perines with smaller areolae and surfaces with abundant filaments (Fig. 2C, D). These characteristics of *P. falciforme* spores and sporangia agree with those previously report by Passarelli et al. (2010) and Wal et al. (2021).

Given the above differences in leaves, sporangia, and perines, we conclude that the Costa Rican and Panamanian plants previously treated by Moran (1995) as *Blechnum christii* (= *Parablechnum christii*) represent a new, undescribed species, one quite distinct from *P. falciforme*. Accordingly, these plants are described here as new.

TAXONOMIC TREATMENT

Parablechnum talamancanum S. Molino & R. C. Moran, sp. nov. TYPE: Costa Rica.

Heredia: Southwest slope of Volcán Barva along trail from Sacramento, 10° 8' N, 84° 7' W, 2650 m, 26 Apr. 1986, *M. H. Grayum* 7389 (holotype, CR [barcode] CR-135885!; isotype, MO [bc] MO-3496899!). Figures 2A–B, 3, 4.

Diagnosis. *Parablechnum talamancanum* S. Molino & R. C. Moran differs from *P. falciforme* (Liebm.) Gasper & Salino by its coriaceous laminae, 7–11 (vs. 12–35) pairs of pinnae, pinnae 2.5–12.3 (vs. 10–22) cm long, pinna length/width ratio of 2.8–7.6 (vs. 4.6–10.6), 28–30 (vs. 19–29) annulus cells, and few or no filaments on the perine surfaces.

Plants terrestrial; *rhizomes* erect, not arborescent, not stoloniferous, scales 10–30 × 3–6 mm, lanceolate, concolorous, pale brown, entire or nearly entire; *fronds* dimorphic, reddish when young. *Sterile fronds* erect; *petiole* 8–30 cm, stramineous or darkened at base, with numerous scales on the base as those of the rhizome; *lamina* 10–32 × 9–20 cm, 1-pinnate, sparsely scaly abaxially, truncate at base, terminal pinna similar to the lateral ones; *pinnae* 7–11 pairs, 2.5–12.3 × 1–3 cm, short-stalked, becoming

basiscopically adnate distally, coriaceous, margins serrate, not becoming involute, base rounded to cordate or subcordate, apex obtuse to acute; *rachis* stramineous to yellowish-brown, transversely rugose, faintly papillose, moderately to densely scaly, the scales whitish to pale straw-colored; *costa* similar to the rachis in color and indument, grooved adaxially, slightly keeled abaxially, *buds* absent; *aerophores* at the pinnae bases ca. 0.5 mm long, oblong. *Fertile fronds* erect, longer than the sterile ones or of similar size, *petiole* 15–45 cm long, stramineous to yellowish-brown, rarely brown; *lamina* 15–40 × 6–15 cm; *pinnae* in the same number as the sterile ones, 4–10 × 0.4–0.5 cm, linear, contracted; *sori* linear, continuous on both sides of the costa; *indusia* linear, continuous, with rectangular cells, slightly lacerated; *sporangia* with 28–30 annulus cells; *spores* monoletate, (61–)66(–76) × (44–)50(–57) μm, with crested–reticulate perines delimiting large polygonal areoles, without or with very scarce filaments on the areole surface, interior of perines spongy, exospore smooth or slightly rough.

Distribution and habitat. Costa Rica, Panama (Fig. 5); cloud forests, especially ones dominated by *Quercus*, in humid, usually exposed areas such as roadsides; 1200–3350 m. This species is reported here for the first time from Panama.

Notes. A similar but smaller species is *Parablechnum werffii* (R. C. Moran) Gasper & Salino, which can be distinguished from *P. talamancanum* by narrower laminae, more numerous pinna pairs (11–25 vs. 7–11 pairs in *P. talamancanum*), smaller pinnae (1.5–3 × 0.6–1 cm vs. 5–10 × 1.4–2.5 cm in *P. talamancanum*), and abaxially glabrous rachises and costae (versus scaly in *P. talamancanum*).

Parablechnum talamancanum also resembles *P. schiedeanum* (C. Presl) Gasper & Salino, a common species throughout Mesoamerica (Moran, 1995). It differs from *P. talamancanum* by longer leaves (60–200 cm) and entire pinnae except on the apex, where the margin is serrulate (vs. completely serrate in *P. talamancanum*). Another similar Central American species is *P. varians* (Fourn.) A. Wal, S. Molino & Gabriel y Galán, but it differs by atropurpureous leaf axes (vs. pale to dark brown on *P. talamancanum*) and crenulate pinna margins.

The above species, all Mesoamerican, resemble *Parablechnum cordatum* (Desv.) Gasper & Salino, a widely distributed species in the mountainous regions of South America (Tryon & Stolze, 1993). It differs from *P. talamancanum* by having leaves up to 2.5 m long. It represents a species complex that requires further studies to resolve it,

some of which are already underway (e.g., Wal et al., 2021; Molino, 2022). However, *P. cordatum* does not occur in Mesoamerica (Moran, 1995; Mickel & Smith, 2004; Molino, 2022).

Paratypes. COSTA RICA. **Alajuela:** 1/10 mi from crater of Volcán Poás, 13 Aug. 1964 *Woodruff s.n.* (US [bc] US-2551967); along the cart-road from Vara Blanca (between Poás and Barba volcanoes) to La Concordia, 23 July 1923, *Maxon & Harvey 8386* (US [bc] US1182005); above the crater of Volcán Poás, 24 Mar. 1973, *Stolze 1455* (F [bc] C-0616022F, US [bc] US-2776183); Poás Lake, Volcán Poás, 3 June 1928, *Stork 2354* (UC [bc] UC1206727); near the road ca. 2.5 km from Volcán Poás, 15 Aug. 1970, *Lellinger 1623* (US [bc] US-2726493); Palmira, Cantón Alfaro Ruiz, 4 Jan. 1939, *Smith 1409* (NY [bc] NY-04178662); slopes near crater of Volcán Poás, 24 Mar. 1973, *Stolze 1460* (F [bc] C-0616016F, C-0616024F, UC [bc] UC-1444332); Poás Lake, Volcán Poás, 5 June 1928, *Stork 2354* (UC [bc] UC-1020672 image); Volcán Poás, 1907, *Alfaro 11918* (US [bc] US-0834094); *ibidem*, 16 June 1967, *de la Sota 5087* (US [bc] US2551012); *ibidem*, 29 July 1932, *Stork 3346* (UC [bc] UC-1355963); *ibidem*, 16 June 1967, *E. de la Sota 4082* (US [bc] US-2551012). **Cartago:** between Empalme and La Chonta, Km 54, 17 May 1964, *Jiménez 1997* (F [bc] C-0616019F, NY [bc] NY-4178666); Cerro de La Carpintera, Feb. 1924, *Standley 34450* (US [bc] US-1154842); Cerro de la Muerte; 1 km NW of Villa Mills on Interamerican Highway, behind Hotel La Georgina, 8 Aug. 1967, *Lellinger 851* (US [bc] US-2589683A); oak forest north of Irazu, 27 Mar. 1928, *Stork 1291* (MO [bc] MO-5423253, UC [bc] UC-1618580); North 10 km from Cerro de la Muerte, 30 Aug. 1983, *Saiki CR-93* (F [bc] C-0616171F); Pan American Highway, San Cristobal Finca, 34 miles from Cartago, 11 Jul. 1961, *Brown 84* (F [bc] C-0616178F); Santa Clara de Cartago, no date, *Lankester 710* (US [bc] US-1207110); Volcán Turrialba, 28 Mar. 1923, *Torres 13* (US [bc] US-1315522); *ibidem*, 26 Feb. 1924, *Torres 128* (US [bc] US-1315615). **Heredia:** Barva, Parque Nacional Braulio Carrillo, Cordillera Central, Volcán Barva, 8 Jan. 2005, *Lépiz 546* (MO [bc] MO-5858614); Parque Nacional Braulio Carrillo, 6 Nov. 1986, *Hennipman et al. s.n.* (L [bc] L-1004206); *ibidem*, 6 Nov. 1986, *Hennipman et al. 6730* (UC [bc] UC-1586645); *ibidem*, transect trail between OTS-Station La Selva and Volcan Barva, 17 May 2003, *Kluge 6816* (GOET [bc] GOET-049357! image); Cordillera Central, Vara Blanca, Camino al Volcán Poás y rumbo a Cariblanco, 2 Mar. 1995, *Rojas 1701* (MO [bc] MO-5893923!); *ibidem*, 6 Feb. 1890, *Pittier 1921* (US [bc] US-0834093!; NY [bc] NY-

4178665!); On the SW slopes of Volcan Barva (formerly Barba), above Sacramento and along the road to the National Park, 3 Feb. 1982, *Burger 11397* (F [bc] C-0616174F, C-0616175F); Volcán Barva, 29 July 1926, *Valerio 36* (US [bc] US-1315908); Yerba Buena, northeast of San Isidro, 22–28 Feb. 1926, *Standley & Valerio 50051* (US [bc] US-1308364). **Puntarenas:** La Palma, 5 June 1926, *Valerio 115* (US [bc] US-1316844). **San José:** along Panamerican Highway in the Cordillera de Talamanca, Villa Mills, 15 Sep. 1961, *Weber 6241* (US [bc] US-2722148); detrás de La Georgina, Carretera Panamericana Sur, 28 Jul. 1965, *Jiménez 3405* (F [bc] C-0616176F); Dota, Carretera Interamericana, km 72, ca. 1 km Sur de Iyok Ami, 15 July 2013, *Rojas et al. 10421* (MACB); Dota, Copey, área no protegida, ojo de Agua, 0.5–3 Km del cruce, rumbo a Providencia, 24 Aug. 2004, *Rojas 5879* (MO [bc] MO-6397838); Dota, Cordillera de Talamanca, camino a San Gerardo de Dota, entrada por Jaboncillo, 17 Sep. 1994, *Rojas 2715* (MO [bc] MO-5858854; NY [bc] NY-4178663; UC [bc] UC-1214980); Las Nubes, 20–22 Mar. 1924, *Standley 38468* (US [bc] US-1215268); massif of Cerro de la Muerte, 5 July 2002, *Kluge 2044a* (GOET [bc] GOET-049358); Pérez Zeledón, páramo, área no protegida, Villa Mills, entre la Georgina y las torres, 8 Jan. 2005, *Rojas 6348* (MO [bc] MO-6397048). PANAMA. **Bocas del Toro:** small stream leading W from Cerro Fábrega into the Valle del Silencio, 11 Mar. 2006, *Monro & Knapp 5276*, (MO [bc] MO-3217858). **Chiriquí:** Bugaba, Las Nubes, 5.5 km NW of Río Chiriquí Viejo, W of Cerro Punta, 27 Feb. 1973, *Busey 668* (F [bc] C-0616025F, MO [bc] MO-2144399); NW of Boquete, Cerro Horqueta, 13 Dec. 1966, *Dwyer et al. 471* (MO [bc] MO-1869807); top of high ridge N of summit of Volcán Barú, "Cerro Pavon," 15 Mar. 1979, *Hammel 6431* (MO [bc] MO-3519884); trail from Cerro Punta to Bajo Grande, 28 May 1970, *Armond 13* (MO [bc] MO-2290809); western slopes of Cerro Respingo, NE of Cerro Punta village, 15 June 1971, *Webster 16596* (MO [bc] MO-3621395). *Sine loc.*, no date, *J. J. Cooper s.n.* (US [bc] US-1544303).

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Liebmann s.n. [Pl. Mex. 2343, Fl. Mex. 775] (lectotype, designated by Smith [1981: 58]: C [bc] C-10021570 image!).

Lomaria deflexa Liebm., Kongel. Danske Vidensk. Selsk. Skr., Naturvidensk. Math. Afd., ser. 5, 1: 236. 1849, nom. illeg., non *L. deflexa* Colenso, Tasmanian J. Nat. Sci. 2: 178, 1844. TYPE: México. Oaxaca: between Totontepec & Trapiche de la Concepción, [no date], *F. M. Liebmann s.n.* [Pl. Mex. 2341, Fl. Mex. 770] (lectotype, designated by Smith [1981: 58], C not seen; isotype, fragm. US-1406165!).

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Selected additional specimens examined. COSTA RICA. **Alajuela:** around summit and old crater lake of Volcán Poás, 6 July 1962, *Mickel 2423* (US [bc] US-2589072A). **Cartago:** Cerro de la Muerte, “Madre Selva”, 24.5 km NW of La Asunción near Km 67 on Interamerican highway, 11 Aug. 1967, *Lellinger 888* (US [bc] US-2589678A, US-2589679A). **Guanacaste:** Liberia, Parque Nacional Guanacaste, sendero casa Frank, entre el cruce a Cerro Cacao y la quebrada, 10 Aug. 2007, *Rojas & Araya 7823* (CR [bc] CR-263286). **Heredia:** Barva, Falls of Chinchona, near Vara Blanca, 30 Jul. 1961, *Brown 210A* (F [bc] C-0616179F). **Limón:** Cerro Chirripó, 25 Aug. 1967, *Evans et al. 158* (US [bc] US-2589685A; US-2589686A). **Puntarenas:** 5 June 1926, La Palma, *Lehmann 115* (CR [bc] CR-38520). **San José:** Alajuelita, San Antonio Z.P. Cerros de Escazú, Cima de cerro Cedral, Estación del Instituto costarricense de Electricidad, 2 July 2007, *Chacón et al. 890* (CR [bc] CR-255424). EL SALVADOR. **Santa Ana:** Bosque Montecristo, 7 Nov. 1977, *Seiler 196* (F [bc] C-0616169F). **Morazán:** 28 Mar. 1979, *Seiler 990* (NY! [bc]; F [bc] C-0616170F). GUATEMALA. **Alta Verapaz:** Río Chió about 2–4 km. SW of Cobán, 31 Jan.–8 Feb. 1969, *Williams et al. 40722* (NY, 2 sheets). **Chimaltenago:** above Las Calderas, 3 Jan. 1939, *Standley 61943* (F [bc] C-

0616132F). **Chiquimula:** between Miramundo and summit of Montaña Miramundo, between Jalapa and Mataquescuintla, 6 miles south of Miramundo, 5 Dec. 1939, *Steyermark 32728* (F [bc] C-0616143F). **Huehuetenango:** Nentón, Bendición de Dios, Montaña Virgen, 12 Dec. 2006, *Jiménez Barrios 639* (MO [bc] MO-6273960). **Quetzaltenango:** Mun. De Zunil, along dirt road above Aldea Chuimucubal, northwest slopes of Pico Zunil, 3 Jan. 2006, *Quedensley 2791* (NY). **Quiché:** 1942, *Aguilar 1214* (F [bc] C-0616131F). **San Marcos:** Cerro Tumbador, Sierra Madre Mountains, about 15 km west of San Marcos, 15 Dec. 1962, *Williams et al. 23057* (F [bc] C-0616151F, C-0616152F, US [bc] US-2425331, US-2425337). **HONDURAS. Francisco Morazán:** Cerro de Uyuca, 10–20 Mar. 1951, *Morton 7214* (US [bc] US-2017120). **Intibucá:** La Esperanza, between Pela Naríz and Calaveras, 12 km from La Esperanza, 7 Mar. 1969, *Molina 24118* (F [bc] C-0616155F, C-0616156F). **La Paz:** between Florida and El Ceron, 7 km from Marcala, 6 Mar. 1969, *Molina 24092* (F [bc] C-0616528F, US [bc] US-3695436). **Ocatepeque:** El Moral on Cordillera Merendón, 27 Aug. 1968, *Molina 22286* (F [bc] C-0616526F, C-0616527F). **MÉXICO. Chiapas:** 1902, *Münch 27* (P [bc] P-01623361, P-01623362). **Chihuahua:** E. of Monserrat, May 1841, *F. M. Liebmann s.n.* (US [bc] US-0474921). **Guerrero:** Dist. Mina, Gro., Toro Muerto, 1 May 1939, *Hinton 14207* (F [bc] C-0616127F, US [bc] US-1748786). **Hidalgo:** 11 km al S de Tenango de Doria, sobre carretera a Metepec, 14 Jan. 1973, *Rzedowski 30211* (NY). **Jalisco:** Barranca de Chinanila, May 1871, *Liebmann s.n.* (P [bc] P-00627589). **Mexico:** Dist. Of Telmascaltepec, La Sierrita, 3 July 1933, *Hinton 3470* (NY, UC [bc] UC-1162741, US [bc] US-1792099). **Nuevo León:** Dist. Galeana, Gro., Teotepec, 21 May 1939, *Hinton 14204* (US [bc] US-1748806). **Oaxaca:** Cerro de Sempoaltepec, no date, *Liebmann s.n.* (B, [bc] B-200031041 [syntype]); *ibidem* (BM, [bc] BM-00769807 [syntype]); *ibidem* (C, [bc] C-10020648!); *ibidem* (C, [bc] C-10020649); *ibidem* (P, [bc] P-00627589 [syntype]). **Puebla:** Distr. Galeana, Gro, Loc. Teotepec, 21 Feb. 1939, *Hinton 14303* (NY, 2 sheets). **Sinaloa:** Mun. Mazatlan Villa de Flores, San Pedro de los Encinos, Sierra Mazateca, 22 Nov. 2001, *Munn-Estrada & Mendoza 1681* (NY, 2 sheets). **Veracruz:** Nov. 1908, *Sandoval 29* (F [bc] C-0616122F). **NICARAGUA. Nueva Segovia:** Mpio. Jalapa, Cerro Jesús, 7 Jul. 2012, *I. Coronado et al. 6676* (MO [bc] MO-6710038, MO-6710039). **PANAMA. Prov. Chiriquí:** 12 miles above Boquete on road to Volcán Barú, 18 May 1976, *Croat 3488* (MO-2623118). **Prov. Coclé:** La Mesa, above El Valle de Antón, ca. 2 km W of Cerro Pílon, 20 Jul. 1976, *Croat 37445* (MO [bc] MO-2628706)

Acknowledgments. We are grateful to the Synthesys+ programme, Cuatrecasas Travel Award, and the Field Museum Visiting Scholar, all awarded to SM, to visit the P, US and F, respectively. We also thank MO and NY for receiving us during research visits and for their help, and to C for providing photos of the type material of *Parablechnum falciforme*. SM received support from a Santander-UCM pre- and post-doctoral contract (CT27/18). This work was also funded by the research grants PID2021-127118NA-I00 of the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation and PR44/21-29930 of the Santander-UCM research program. WT received support from the US National Science Foundation under Grant DEB-2045319.

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FIGURE LEGENDS:

Figure 1. Type specimen (consisting of two sheets) of *Blechnum christii*, a replacement name for *Lomaria spissa* Christ, nom. illeg., non Fée. Note the numbering in pencil on the lower right of each specimen as “1/2” and “2/2.” A. Sheet one of two, P-01623169; B. Sheet two of two, P-01623170).

Figure 2. Spores of two species of *Parablechnum* from Central America. A, B. *Parablechnum talamancanum* (R. E. Woodruff s.n., US-2551967). —A. General view of the spore. —B. Detail of a broken part of the perine, showing the exospore. C, D. *Parablechnum falciforme* (R. Torres et al. 17654, VT-198685). C. —General view of the spore. —D. Detail of a broken part of the perine, showing the exospore beneath. Scale bars: A 36 μm , B 18.5 μm , C 28 μm , D 17 μm .

Figure 3. *Parablechnum talamancanum*. —A. Habit. —B. Sterile pinna, adaxial side. (M. H. Grayum 7389, MO-3496899). —C. Aerophore indicated by an arrow (C. Weber 6241, US2722148). —D. Scale from the abaxial side of the costa. —E. Rhizome scale (A. Rojas et al. 10421, MACB). Scale bar: A 20 mm; B 6 mm; C 1.2 mm; D 0.4 mm; E 7 mm.

Figure 4. Habit of *Parablechnum talamancanum*. Note longer-petiolate, erect fertile leaf. (Costa Rica, photo by R. C. Moran).

Figure 5. Distribution of *Parablechnum talamancanum*.